

D4.3 INTEGRATED AND VALIDATED VERSION OF ENVISION PLATFORM

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

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Executive Summary

This document aims at describing the progress and accomplishments achieved in WP4 and it tries to give a tour to the ENVISION platform functionalities that were implemented. Furthermore, the deliverable includes a description how the architecture was adapted based on the needs and requirements of the integration.

Specifically, the sections of this deliverables are:

Section 1 – Progress towards ENVISION platform: Contains the progress made by the technical team.

Section 2 – ENVISION Platform: Contains the aspects of the ENVISION platform, exploring its integrated services and providing an in-depth overview why the ENVISION platform can be characterised as Area Monitoring System.

Section 3 – Tour to ENVISION platform’s functionalities: Contains some user interfaces of the platform in order to give the reader a feeling of the environment and at the same time to demonstrate the main ENVISION functionalities.

Section 4 – Next Steps: Contains a brief description of the next steps that are planned after the release of the first version of the ENVISION platform.

1 Progress towards ENVISION Platform

ENVISION aims to develop a ready-to-market commercial platform of services, co-designed and co-created with PAs and CBs, fit to address their needs. In particular, ENVISION provides PAs and CBs with a robust and cost-efficient set of services allowing them to monitor continuously and systematically the agricultural land, shifting the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific fields and dates (or time window) to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring. Acting as a trailblazer for organisations that monitor environmental- and climate- friendly agricultural practices stemming from CAP, ENVISION increases the effectiveness of risk-based analysis for the selection of farms for inspection; increases the efficiency and transparency of PAs and CBs' procedures when implementing the CAP; reduces the number of on-site visits by performing more targeted controls and reduces operational and administrative costs.

1.1 Development methodology

During this period, several adaptations and modifications have been performed in the platform, not only in the frontend but also in the backend of the toolbox in order for the integrated and validated version of the platform to be delivered.

Several calls have been performed among the technical team and the service providers in order to define the main actions that should be followed to accomplish the integration with the various external components and investigate/ explore alternatives in the case of failure.

Furthermore, the technical team asked all the partners (not only the business cases) to go through the initial platform and provide feedback focused on its operability, improvement and stability. Regular meetings were held in order to facilitate the testers to get more familiar with the functionalities of the platform and to collect issues/ suggestions. These issues were categorised, prioritised and reported to the issue tracking system Trello which is integrated with the internal backlog of the technical team Jira.

Figure 1: Trello, ENVISION issue tracking system

1.2 Releases

In order to develop a robust and solid integrated and validated version of the ENVISION platform, and based on the iterations/ meetings that were performed, the technical team prepared a timeplan with the actions/ developments that would perform (releases).

□ ENVISION – Version v0.6.0

- **Bug**
 - ENV-100 Keep UTF-8 encoding after EPSG conversion
 - ENV-89 Shp upload alignment
- **Change**
 - ENV-106 Expand shp with sowing and harvest date
- **Improvement**
 - ENV-108 Appropriately disable/enable "Import" button in ShapefileImport view
 - ENV-105 Inform PAs about result availability in 5-9 days for imported parcels
 - ENV-104 Retain yod information upon returning from parcel inspection to overview page
 - ENV-99 Create crops lookup endpoint
 - ENV-66 Parcel info - Graph
 - ENV-63 Parcel info - Too many digitals
- **New Feature**
 - ENV-68 Parcel info - Explanations
 - ENV-61 Show parcel boundaries in overview page when clicking a parcel
- **Story**
 - ENV-101 Create parcel list endpoint
 - ENV-56 Handle parcels import process
- **Task**
 - ENV-86 There is a hardcoded API key for the base maps in the frontend
 - ENV-62 Don't show the parcel info popup when there is no parcel at the selected location

□ ENVISION – Version v0.6.1

- **Change**
 - ENV-112 Remove Cyprus mapper
 - ENV-111 Increase allowed upload size
 - ENV-110 Remove plot id and n plot parcel fields

□ ENVISION – Version v0.7.0

- **New Features**
 - Integration with NOA database to retrieve results
 - Integration with geosrbia to retrieve parcel info
 - Integration with AgroApps to retrieve NDVI, Yield estimation and Organic results
 - Ability to download template files: Geosrbia csv, parcels shape
 - Ability to upload SOC layers
 - Display the SOC and Yield Estimation layers

- Ability to export pdf for Paying Agencies
 - **Improvements**
 - Improve parcel info as per the: crop classification and Traffic Light
 - Display units on all metrics
 - Add a new business case for UK
 - **Fixes**
 - Allow different Paying Agencies to use the same unique id
 - Fix geoserver layer generation from uploaded raster files
 - Fix the default area unit on GeoSerbia data
 - Various fixes and changes while adapting to new NOA DB schema
- **ENVISION – Version v0.8.0**
 - **New Features**
 - Allow filtering on potential problems (Smart sampling)
 - Add case specific classification colors to parcel layers
 - Alert paying agencies for potential problems by email
 - Add GDPR consent popup
 - Add collector for rasters
 - Re-enable export to pdf functionality
 - **Improvements**
 - Display potential problems count in parcel summary (bell icon)
 - Allow PAs to import parcels only for the current year
 - Improve parcel summary pop-up
 - Implement proper logging on the backend
 - **Bugfixes**
 - Fix old NOA corrupt data
 - Replace base map with a FOSS
 - Fix sidebar position when not on top of the page
 - Various bugfixes on the UI and the backend
- **ENVISION – Version v0.8.1**
 - **Fixes**
 - Fix the integration with the OCTOPUSH service hub
 - Integration of open-source license

2 ENVISION Platform

In this section presents the aspects of the ENVISION platform, exploring its integrated services and providing an in-depth overview why the ENVISION platform can be characterised as Area Monitoring System. The Add-on development tool is presented in the respective Deliverable 5.8 Add-on development showcase and capacity building report.

2.1 ENVISION as an open-source platform

The ENVISION platform is an open-source platform and will be licensed under the MIT Licence¹. Permission is granted, free of charge, to any person obtaining a copy of this software and associated documentation files, to deal in the Software without restriction, including without limitation the rights to use, copy, modify, merge, publish, distribute, sublicense, and/or sell copies of the Software, and to permit persons to whom the Software is furnished to do so, subject to the following conditions: The above copyright notice and this permission notice shall be included in all copies or substantial portions of the Software.

The open-source code can be found here: <https://git.draxis.gr/open-source/envision-2020> and <https://zenodo.org/record/8334122>

2.2 Integration of the services

The ENVISION project places users at its heart, guiding evolution from initial requirements identification to its technical development. This user-centric approach ensured that the ENVISION platform was crafted to align with users' needs, ensuring usability, functionality, and market acceptance.

Although each business case scenario may vary with distinct needs, the consortium has chosen to develop a unified platform, seamlessly integrating products and services from all services providers. This strategy aims to offer a comprehensive suite of services to users across varied business contexts. The platform is organized into five specific cases/ accounts, namely UK, Serbia, Lithuania, Cyprus, and Flanders. This structure ensures that each user sees only the imported parcels pertinent to their Area of Interest (AOI). All the services (and thus the relevant fields) are accessible from all cases. However, based on the services that they have used/ tested during the pilot implementation phase, they received the respective results/ outcomes. For instance, while Lithuanian PA users can view the results from DP1-DP3 (since that was the aim of their business case), they were also able to view the other service fields, like the distinction farming practices, though without detailed results (since the service has not been provided for their case).

On the technical side, while the platform supports various services providers, it operates atop a unified main database, ensuring consistency and integration. The ENVISION backend comprises two primary components: the Business Layer and the Storage Layer. The Business Layer, which is the heart of the system, processes data from both end-users and services providers. Despite the varied input sources, all data converge into a singular, central database, ensuring a seamless user experience. This Business Layer communicates with the frontend via the HTTP/TLS protocol through the Web API.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License

End-users interface with the Business Layer via the Authentication Service (Keycloak) using the OpenID Connect protocol. As for the product import process, despite service providers using varied methods – be it via the Web API or SSH tunnelling – all roads lead to a single, integrated database, underscoring the platform’s cohesive nature.

2.3 ENVISION as an Area Monitoring System (AMS)

An Area Monitoring System (AMS) is typically characterized by its ability to continuously observe, track, and assess a defined geographical area for specific parameters or changes over time. The ENVISION platform is defined as AMS since it covers the following characteristics:

1. **Continuous Observation:** The ENVISION platform constantly monitors a specific area, providing real-time or near-real-time data about that area, mainly using satellite data.
2. **Geographical Focus:** The platform is designed to cover a defined geographical region (i.e. Serbia case), or even an entire country (i.e. Lithuanian, Cypriot and Flanders cases).
3. **Sentinel satellite and Data Collection:** The platform utilizes Sentinel satellite data in order to track and assess agricultural activities and practices on the agricultural areas (i.e. crop identification, mowing detection, distinction of organic farming practices, etc.).
4. **Alerts and Notifications:** In case of any deviations or detections, the platform alerts the end-users through email.
5. **Historical Data Storage:** The ENVISION platform stores data over time, allowing for analysis.
6. **Integration capabilities:** The ENVISION platform can be integrated with other systems or databases to enhance its monitoring capabilities.
7. **Scalability:** The ENVISION platform can scale its operations, expanding its coverage area or adding more parameters to monitor as needed.
8. **Interactivity:** In the ENVISION platform, users can set specific monitoring parameters (i.e. view the misclassified parcels), zoom into specific areas (i.e. selected parcel).

3 Tour to the ENVISION Platform

This section details the second version of the ENVISION platform that will be used by the business cases partners to test and validate its provided services and functionalities. This last release of the platform is as complete as needed until the next defined version.

The ENVISION platform is accessible through the following link: <https://platform.envision-h2020.eu/>. The administrator (technical team) has already generated accounts for each business case in order for the users to have access to the web application.

Figure 2: Log in

Following the log in of the user, the GDPR window pops up.

After the user has given their consent to the Privacy Policy, they land on the overview screen.

Figure 3: Overview

In the overview, the users are able to view all the imported parcels of the Area of Interest (AOI). If in the imported information the categorisation (organic, conventional) is filled in, then the parcels are coloured differently (green – organic, purple – conventional, grey – not defined). In that way, the users are able to identify easily and quickly the type of the parcel.

Furthermore, in the overview, the users are able to visualise layers on top of the map and perform specific queries to retrieve information with regards to the potential problems such as misclassifications and mowing events or the level of compliance. The users are also able to see previously imported declarations by selecting their preferred year and they can search a parcel either with the parcel ID, the Applicant ID or the Declared Crop Code.

Figure 4: Parcel information

When the users click on a parcel, they can see the above information (Parcel ID, Declared Crop Code, Declared Area, Farming Practices and Applicant ID). In contrast to the previous version, the notification bell was added as a new element. When hovering over the bell, a text box displays information about the detected potential problems regarding the parcel. Finally, the OPEN button redirects the user to the monitoring screen of the selected parcel, as seen below.

Figure 5: Parcel view

In the parcel view screen, the users can see general information about the parcel as well as the outcomes of the ENVISION services.

General Info

Parcel ID: 1011787453-117575-2783-1
 Applicant ID: 1011787453
 Year of Declaration: 2022

Farming Practices: Not Available

Declared Crop Code: 130
 Crop Classification: ● ● ● (Date: Not Available)
 Crop Type Category
 Highest-level : Not Available
 Middle-level: Not Available
 Lowest-level: Not Available

Declared Area: 38854.9 ha
 Estimated Area: 38850.21 ha

Soil Organic Carbon: Not Available

Figure 6: Parcel General Information

In the General Info block the user can view the following:

- Parcel ID
- Applicant ID
- Year of Declaration
- Farming Practices: The declared type of farming practices (organic or conventional)
- Declared Crop Code
- Crop Classification (along with the respective traffic light system)
- Crop Type Category
- Declared Area
- Estimated Area: The area that is estimated from the ENVISION platform
- Soil Organic Carbon

Figure 7: Parcel view in the map

The map in this screen is responsive. This means that the users are able to see the parcel in zoom but they are also able to zoom out and see the provided results in a wider area.

Figure 8: Filters

The users are able to search for a parcel using the filters depicted in the above figure. In addition, the users can apply on the map the NDVI layer, which is derived from the EO-based services.

Figure 9: ENVISION Services

The ENVISION services with regards to CAP compliance are presented in the above figure. The users are able to see the results derived from the algorithms along with the respective accuracy.

More specifically, the user can see the number of crops identified on the parcel and the respective crop classification with the level of confidence for the result. Also, the system presents the detected mowing events, the estimated dates that the potential mowing event took place and the level of accuracy regarding this probability. Finally, the user has access in various data about the parcel, such as the proximity to water sources, level of soil erosion and others. If a service does not have any result to demonstrate, then a message “Not Available” appears to the respective box.

Figure 10: Graph

Furthermore, the users are able to see time-series of crop growth monitoring indices (NDVI, NDWI, PSRI) and some measures of statistical analysis. In addition to the previous version, the dates on which the highest and lowest statistical value was measured for every index are presented on the graph.

Another functionality that was added, is the export one. The users are able to export the viewed parcel along with its general information.

General Info

Parcel ID: 1005255597-114569-4690-2
 Applicant ID: 1005255597
 Year of Declaration: 2022

Farming Practices: Not Available

Declared Crop Code: 130
 Crop Classification: Not Available (Date: Not Available)
 Crop Type Category
 Highest-level: Not Available
 Middle-level: Not Available
 Lowest-level: Not Available

Declared Area: 444.7 ha
 Estimated Area: 451.66 ha

Soil Organic Carbon: Not Available

Figure 11: Parcel export

Figure 12: Import functionality

The users are able to import their parcels in the form of a shapefile and set the year of declaration. However, it is only allowed to declare a parcel on one of the two previous years. This means, that when a user imports a new parcel, they can set as the year of declaration the current or the previous year only. Furthermore, the users are able to download a shp. file template in order to see what type of information should be included (i.e. Cyprus, Lithuania and UK) and specific instructions are provided to the Serbian business case (ANNEX – IMPORT PARCELS).

Nonetheless, the system stores all previous imports and the user has access to the historical data from the overview page.

Figure 13: Use case assignment

Finally, each user is assigned to a specific use case (i.e. Lithuania). However, the platform offers the possibility to assign more than one cases in a specific user (SuperUser). This process is implemented only for the administrator of the platform (the technical team).

4 Mobile App Wireframes

In this section, the wireframes for the mobile application are being presented, illustrating the main features of the app.

The initial page the user sees is the log in page.

ENVISION APP

Username

Password

[Forgot Password?](#)

Log in

Don't have account?
[Create an account](#)

Figure 17: Log in

In the case the user does not have an account, they can create one through the sign up page.

EU

Username

Email

Applicant ID

Password

Create

Figure 18: Sign up

After the user has created an account and has logged in, they land on the overview page.

Figure 19: Overview page

In the main page the user can see on an interactive map the parcels that they have declared. They can search for a specific parcel or they can tap on a parcel on the map and view the relevant information (Declared Area, Crop Classification, Parcel ID).

Under the map, there is a menu with the main components of the application, which are the Fields, the Calendar, the Files and the Profile.

When the user taps on the Profile icon, they are redirected to the account settings. More specifically, they can view or edit the applicant ID, change the password, log out or delete the account.

Figure 20: Account settings

In order to change the password, the user is asked to insert their old password and their new password twice, as seen below.

✕

Change Password

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor.

Old Password

●●●●●●●●

New Password

●●●●●●●●

Confirm New Password

●●●●●●●●

Confirm

Figure 21: Change password

The user can, also, change the username and the email of the account.

✕ Save Changes

EU

Username

Example Username

Email

example@gmail.com

✕ Save Changes

The email will change.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

No Yes

Figure 22: Edit username & email

In the Fields component, there is a list of all the parcels the user has imported.

Figure 23: Imported parcels

When the users tap on a field, they are redirected to the monitoring page of that parcel. On this page, the user can see the crop growth monitoring indices (NDVI) of the parcel, the declared area, the crop type and the dates of the important events that occurred on the parcel.

Figure 24: Parcel review

In the calendar component, the user can choose to see the dates of the declarations or other actions that took place for the imported parcels.

Figure 25: Calendar

Finally, when the user taps on the plus button, the camera switches on so as the user can take a picture and upload it on the application. The picture provides the application with the geospatial data of the parcel and a timestamp and it confirms the event that occurred on the parcel.

Figure 26: Take a picture functionality

The user can upload various pictures and pdf files regarding one parcel. These are accessible through the files button on the main menu. The user can insert a parcel id and view all the files that have been uploaded regarding that parcel.

Figure 27: Files

5 Next Steps

Our plan is to continue improving the platform both from a feature perspective, but also from a perspective of performance and quality of provided information and user experience. This version is the second one, which also includes the integration with the service providers and any external system that will be used during the business cases implementation phase. This version was built in order to collect valuable feedback and better understanding of the users' needs and processes. Our aim is to build on top of this version and further improve it the next months in order to deliver a ready-to-market solution.

In addition, following the meetings with the farmers and developers and the feedback that will be collected, the mobile application and the Add-on Development tool will be built during the next months.

In essence, the ENVISION platform has been developed incorporating all the provided services as well as the following elements:

- **User-friendly interface:** The interface has been designed in a user-friendly manner that serves as the gateway for users to interact with the ENVISION services and functionalities. Both the first screen (general overview) and the second one (parcels detailed information) are designed in a simple way offering to the end-users all the relevant and needed information. **All the business cases have the same screens and functionalities.** However, each business case visualizes and consumes the services and the relevant products defined in the DoA. In order to provide modular components and a structured approach to UI development, ENVISION has used the frontend framework Vue.js and its Vuetify material design component in order to build a responsive and interactive user interface.
- **Query tools:** Query tools have been implemented within the platform to allow users to interact with and retrieve data from the storage layer. This includes search functionalities (i.e. the user can search an imported parcel through the applicant/ parcel id) and tools that facilitate efficient data querying (i.e. in case of Lithuanian/ Cypriot business case the user can make a query to retrieve the parcels that are misclassified, and in case of Serbian business case the user can request to view the organic and the non-organic parcels). In order to do so PostgreSQL and PostGIS extension, as well as Axios have been used, which allows clients to request only the specific data needed.
- **Integration with backend logic layer:** The platform has been integrated with a centralized backend logic layer that combines all the different databases for the three services providers. Therefore, the frontend of the ENVISION platform is capable of forming requests and communicating effectively with the backend to process user queries and requests. RESTful APIs have been used in order to establish communication between the frontend and the backend.
- **Data visualization:** The information imported and the results derived from the services are presented in a meaningful way. Interactive map controls, graphs and tables are employed to enhance the visual representation of information. ENVISION makes use of data visualization library such as Apache ECharts for creating interactive charts and graphs.
- **Geospatial visualization:** Given the geospatial nature of data, interactive map controls have been incorporated that allow users to visualize geospatial information. Features such as

zooming, clickable areas and overlays have been implemented to provide a comprehensive view of the spatial data along with the relevant results. ENVISION leverage the Mapbox GL JS mapping and OpenLayers libraries.

- **Security measures:** Security measures have been implemented to safeguard user data and ensure the integrity of interactions between frontend and backend layers. This includes data encryption, and user authentication. Specifically, HTTPS has been implemented for secure communication and OAuth2 (keycloak) has been utilized for user authentication and authorization.
- **Scalability:** The platform has been developed with scalability to accommodate growing data volumes and increasing user interactions. Such an example is the case of Lithuania in which more than 1.000.000 parcels have been imported. In order to achieve efficient deployment and scaling, ENVISION uses containerization with Docker.

However, more layers would be incorporated per business case in order for the end-users to have a more complete platform as an operational system.

ANNEX – IMPORT PARCELS

Lithuania, Cyprus and UK

The shp file template for the aforementioned business cases includes the following columns. However, each business case should fill in the columns that apply for its case. Therefore, no column is characterized as mandatory field.

- OBJECTID
- APPLICANT
- UNIQUE_ID
- CROP_CODE
- AREA
- ORGANIC
- TRANS_YEAR
- SOW_DATE
- HARV_DATE
- LAST_DECL
- DECL_YEAR
- LAST_EVAL
- VAL_METHOD
- EVAL_RES
- EVAL_YEAR
- SHAPE_LENG
- SHAPE_AREA

OBJECTID	APPLICANT	UNIQUE_ID	CROP_CODE	AREA	ORGANIC	TRANS_YEAR	SOW_DATE	HARV_DATE	LAST_DECL	DECL_YEAR	LAST_EVAL	VAL_METHOD	EVAL_RES	EVAL_YEAR	SHAPE_AREA

Figure 14: Shp file template

The Serbian case

1. Select “Import Parcels” from the “hamburger” icon on the top left corner

2. Click on the “DOWNLOAD TEMPLATE” button

3. Fill up the csv template file and save it
4. Select the csv file, then click “IMPORT”

5. Wait for the parcels to be integrated from Geoserbjia
6. Check for any errors. i.e. During the import process in the picture bellow, one parcel failed to be imported due to invalid input data. The rest of the parcels were successfully imported

Import Parcels

CSV

Completed

Errors (Total: 1) ^

Latest Errors

3:44:23 PM - Failed to get parcel from geose Serbia ('MUNICIPALITY': 'Alibunar', 'CADASTRAL_MUNICIPALITY': 'Dobrica', 'CADASTRAL_NUMBER': nan, 'CROP': nan, 'ORGANIC': nan, 'ORGANIC_TRANS_YEAR': <NA>, 'SHAPE_LENGTH': nan, 'SHAPE_AREA': nan): Invalid value. Property: cadastralNumber. Value: nan. Set: Alibunar, Dobrica, nan

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Once the integration process has been completed, the services will start calculating the results.

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